

SATISFACTORY

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Situated and Attractive Information Exchange Techniques for Workers

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
3D	3-Dimensional
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
Hi-Fi	High-Fidelity
HMD	Head-Mounted Display
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MR	Mixed Reality
REST	Representational State Transfer
UI	User Interface

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme (H2020), reporting the results of the activities carried out by WP3. SatisFactory aims to develop an ecosystem of innovative technological components that would assist the daily operations of the people working at industrial environment. More specifically the developments of SatisFactory will be demonstrated to three diverse shop floors from discrete manufacturing (COMAU), batch products manufacturing (SUNLIGHT Systems) and continuous processes (CERTH/CPERI).

The deliverable D3.2 documents a few of the perceived concepts that were selected for elaboration. The details of the entire set of concepts and how they evolved is documented in D2.3 - Social Experience and Gamification techniques for increasing attractiveness. In addition, the deliverable D3.4 - Collaborative Platform for Work Process Support describes how a selected few of these concepts were implemented. The implemented concepts include The Gamification Framework, the Suggestions for Improvement Platform, The Social Interaction Platform and the Protect your Health System. In addition to these concepts, it also describes the use of wearable technology, augmented reality glasses to provide hands free interaction with the system.

D3.2 explains how the user interfaces for the above mentioned systems were designed and how they evolved into their final state. Also, what design decisions had to be taken and why. It describes in an iterative manner how these interfaces progressed to their current state. These interfaces were designed keeping in mind that systems created should not be too intrusive and should be ubiquitous in nature.

1. INTRODUCTION

Task T3.2 deals with designing the interaction between users and the systems, which were selected for implementation in scope of T2.3. In task T2.3, concepts for the enhancement of the working environments are worked out, based on the results of the domain analysis and formulated requirements in WP1. In total, 19 different ideas were worked out. A few of them were selected for elaboration. Finally, four of them were selected for implementation: The Gamification Framework, the Suggestions for Improvement Platform, The Social Interaction Platform and the Protect your Health System. This text documents the respective software deliverables about the user interfaces. The conceptual work behind it is described in D2.3 - Social Experience and Gamification techniques for increasing attractiveness. The corresponding implementation deliverable is D3.4 - Collaborative Platform for Work Process Support.

The interaction concepts developed for the systems align with core ubiquitous computing concepts. Thus, the idea is always to merge virtual and real worlds in a sense that computers are integrated into the workers' world instead of making workers adapt from their well-known processes by introducing traditional computers and changing processes. In this sense, the best solution is when workers even don't notice that they are acting with a computerized system, which is perfectly applied in the Protect your Health system. A less merged, but still ubiquitous, solution is the introduction of tablet computers. These require different design iterations as desktop computer applications, as the Suggestions Platform shows.

Another good example is the use of wearable technology, augmented reality glasses in case of SatisFactory. The glasses are used as visual output device with which the user does not explicitly has to interact. Furthermore, the worker's hands keep free. Finally, this augmented reality approach is a match of integrating virtual content directly to the real world. In the last chapter of this deliverable, we show how the AR glasses could be applied to the other presented concepts.

2. APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY

The interfaces developed for the Satisfactory systems presented in this deliverable were created in an iterative approach according to the ISO 9241-210 process model [ISO 2010] (cf. Figure 1). For more details about it, refer to D1.1 - User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines.

Figure 1: ISO9241-210 Process Model

The parts about understanding the context of use and specifying the user requirements are presented in D1.1 - User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines. This deliverable D3.2 focuses on producing design solutions and evaluating them in order to get new requirements for further iterations of design probes. This was done in several cycles until an acceptable status of the design was reached.

2.1 *PROTOTYPING APPLICATIONS*

Prototypes put something concrete in front of the stakeholders, so that all discussion can be done at the same level and towards a concrete, possible implementation of the system. It is important for prototypes to be visibly unfinished, so people don't waste time discussing about unimportant details but rather about the important general concepts. Prototyping is meant to try out different things. It is explicitly desired to throw away prototypes after usage - another aspect why a prototype should not be too much elaborated.

There are different levels of prototypes:

- A conceptual prototype describes the functionality and design verbally
- A paper prototype is a simple hand-made sketch, either pictures or comic-like sequences of the future screen output
- Static screen outputs display content on a screen, but are without dynamics
- Dynamic simulations simulate simple flows on a screen. The user has the feeling of a real system but no real data processing is going on
- Within the Wizard-of-Oz technique, the future processes are simulated by Person, who are not noticed by the user

There are professional prototyping tools like Balsamiq³ or Axure⁴ available. But linking screenshots within PowerPoint is also a valid approach.

2.2 HUMAN-COMPUTER INTERACTION IN UBIQUITOUS COMPUTING

In his famous paper “The computer for the 21st century” [Weiser 1991], Mark Weiser describes his vision how computer systems will change in the nearer future. Computers will be more integrated in the real world up to the extent that they cannot be identified as computers anymore and the user perceives the environment as intelligent. In Satisfactory, this is applied by the Protect your Health System.

The five core aspects of this ubiquitous computing vision are [Poslad 2009]:

1. Distributed systems: Ubiquitous computing systems consist of several smaller distributed subsystems which are interlinked. The distribution is transparent for the user, thus appearing as a single system to the user.
2. Implicit human-computer interaction: Human interfaces of ubiquitous computing systems are hidden or integrated in the real world. So, users rather interact with the real world than with a computer system. In the optimal case, “they even do not realize to interact with a computerized system but the system understands it as input.” [Schmidt 2000]
3. Context-Awareness: Ubiquitous computing systems adopt to the current environmental, human or virtual context.
4. Autonomy: Ubiquitous computing systems can control their own actions without human intervention.
5. Intelligence: Intelligent systems take into account a model of the physical and human environment and base their decisions upon. This enables them to handle incompleteness, non-determinism and semantics.

Over recent years, some aspects of the ubiquitous computing vision have been introduced in daily life and used for different domains. For example, a modern car consists of several interlinked sensors and computing units which the user does not perceive as computer systems but as part of the car. Using the parking assistance does not require to control a computer system, users only drive their car

³ <https://balsamiq.com/products/mockups/>

⁴ <http://www.axure.com/>

as they normally would do. The car is aware of its location and the surroundings and manages this information without the need for interaction of the user.

In Weiser's initial vision [Weiser 1991], which founded the field of ubiquitous computing, he already presented 3 classes of devices, which should replace computer terminals: tabs, pads and boards. They were differentiated most notably by their size and style of usage.

The researchers at Xerox PARC also built prototypes for every device class in order to explore concepts of use. ParcTab is a device which fits into a palm of the hand and is able to present texts and bitmaps [Schilit et al 1993].

The MPad is the implementation of a *pad* device [Weiser 1993]. In terms of visualization, it provides the same capabilities as a laptop at that time. The main difference is the different form factor: The MPad does not have a keyboard.

Large displays and central projection surfaces have already been used in 1992 in office environments. The new property that the Liveboard system created, was to add direct, stylus-based interactivity [Elrod et al. 1992]. This feature made it the implementation of a ubiquitous computing *board* device. Nowadays, usually smartphones are used as tabs instances, tablet computers as pads instances and public displays as board instances. In the systems presented in this deliverable, the suggestions for improvement systems uses a pad while the gamification framework employs tabs and boards as interfaces.

2.3 **AUGMENTED REALITY**

[Milgram and Kishino, 1994] define approaches which consist of virtual and real parts as mixed reality (MR). Within this, Augmented Reality (AR) "refer[s] to any case in which an otherwise real environment is 'augmented' by means of virtual (computer graphic) objects". [Azuma, 1997] defines augmented reality systems by three characteristics: They combine real and virtual, are interactive in real time and are registered in 3D.

A common way of implementing AR systems is the information lens approach [Fitzmaurice, 1993]. It makes use of handheld display widgets. To achieve a spatial matching, a widget displays the data when it is placed on top of the object. A special kind of information lens is when the widget is semi-transparent. Virtual information and real-world objects look merged to the user. This is often referred to as magic lens or see-through approach [Bier et al., 1993].

[Milgram et al., 1994] based their definition of augmented reality on the use of specific technologies. AR systems started by mainly using head-mounted displays (HMD) [Sutherland, 1968] - displays that users wear on their head. HMDs can display 3-dimensional objects, which change according to the user's head movements. Later, HMDs were miniaturized to the size of glasses [Lukowicz et al., 2001].

2.4 **GUIDELINES FOR MOBILE INTERACTION DESIGN AND UX**

The MyFactory app will run as a kiosk system on a tablet. For this reason, we have decided on using the mobile first approach to develop the app and then build on this foundation for the MyFactoryManagement application, which will be implemented as a web app.

- **Touch target sizes**

An appropriate size for touch targets is crucial to the usability of mobile applications. Bigger targets are easier to hit and improve the usability. Regarding this, we have to take into account the average size of a fingertip, which is about one to two centimeters wide. There are different recommendations for the size of touch targets. Apple recommends a size of minimum 44x44px, Microsoft specifies a target size of 34px and Google's Material Design Standard suggests 48x48 dp. For icons or buttons smaller than the minimum size, it is recommended to expand the touchable area around the element up to the recommended size. The spacing between interactive elements is also important in order to avoid users interacting with adjacent elements. Here Material Design specifies a spacing of 8dp or more between interactive elements.

- **Reachable and noticeable controls**

Interactive elements in a tablet kiosk applications preferably should be placed in a section of the screen where they cannot be obscured by e.g. the keyboard or the user's wrist.

- **Animation and movement**

According to Material Design, movement should always follow a purpose. Transitions and animations should therefore serve to guide the user throughout the application and illustrate the information structure as well as the relations between the elements.

- **Touch Gestures**

Since MyFactory is a hybrid application, the interactions should not rely heavily on touch gestures, especially if they are platform specific or implemented differently across platforms. However, common touch gestures such as swipe to scroll a list should be implemented.

- **Application structure**

For the implementation of the kiosk application, it is very important to display all the essential information on the overview screen, without the need of scrolling. Also for detail-views we favoured an overlay representation in order to keep the main screen always present.

- **Color scheme**

In order to provide a neutral, but engaging color scheme, we oriented ourselves on the Material Design guidelines for UI colors. The standard offers a palette of primary and accent colors along with a set of rules for combining them. When developing a color scheme, first a primary color is chosen. Based on this another color is picked as an accent-color. The primary color will be used on all screens and be the main application color. The accent color will serve to highlight the main interactive elements of the UI. Additionally, we used the traffic light principle in order to signal states and key actions.

2.5 **EVALUATION METHODS**

For evaluating the prototypes, semi-structured interviews, contextual inquiries and think-aloud testing was used.

2.5.1 ***Semi-structured Interviews***

Semi-structured interviews utilize a prepared list of questions, based on literature review, existing domain and problem knowledge, etc. However, it is allowed to stray from the plan if the conversation leads into interesting areas that were not anticipated in the list. The main point is to watch out for interesting remarks and follow up with new, on-the-spot questions to probe deeper.

2.5.2 ***Contextual Inquiries***

Contextual inquiries are specific interviews where users are interviewed in their workplace, while they are working. It is important that the interviewers do not negatively interfere or disturb the user. A kind of master-apprentice relationship develops, where the user has to teach the designer how the work is done. The designer asks questions, trying to learn as much as possible about the process. At the end, he or she makes a summary of what was learned, and the user has to correct or give feedback on this summary.

2.5.3 ***Think-aloud testing***

User testing with thinking aloud is a method wherein a user is asked to complete certain tasks using a prototype of the system. The user has to think aloud while using the system, and openly say whatever comes to his or her mind. This allows the designers to understand the user's mental image (understanding) of the system, and to note where this understanding is different from what the designers intend. The problems thus found are analysed and the design is changed to either match the user's understanding, or to better communicate to the user the intents and actions available through the system's interface.

3. DESIGN OF THE SUGGESTIONS PLATFORM

3.1 PROTOTYPES

For the suggestions for improvement platform, screens for two tablet apps were designed: The **MyFactory App** and the **MyFactoryManagement App**. The first is for the workers, the second is for the decision-makers. This section describes how the designs evolved.

3.1.1 1st Version

For the first version, all screens were first painted by pencil. This was done in five iterations. Between every iteration, there were internal discussions with several team members in which the benefits and drawbacks of the screens were discussed and improvements were worked out. As an example, Figure 4 - Figure 5 present the iterations of the “submit a suggestions” screen.

Figure 2: "Submit a suggestion" screen, 1st iteration

Figure 3: "Submit a suggestion" screen, 2nd iteration

Figure 4: "Submit a suggestion" screen, 3rd iteration

Figure 5: "Submit a suggestion" screen, 4th iteration

It becomes clear that the design was more and more refined. For instance, during the third iteration, the idea of visualizing the main input form as parted paper was introduced. The idea was to be oriented on the traditional agony column approach where suggestions on pieces of paper are put into a letterbox.

Other ideas evolved. For instance, the “back to categories” and “submit suggestion” text were first added to the actual buttons with only small icons. In the next iteration, the texts were completely replaced by the icons. Then, with the third iteration, the combination of keeping the icons on the buttons with texts below them stabilized.

In the fifth iteration, the drawings readability was improved because this was planned to be the final iteration of the first version. For this, other drawing tools were used. At the same time, this fifth iteration also underwent further content evolutions, as Figure 6 shows.

Figure 6: "Submit a suggestion" screen, fifth iteration

The screens of all iterations can be found in Annexes A1.1 - A1.6.

3.1.2 **Evaluation of 1st Version**

The final design presented in Section 3.1.1 was used to conduct a user study with end users. For this, the paintings were scanned and imported into Axure. This way, it was possible to create a clickable prototype out of it, in order to convey the functionality. Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the interaction maps for MyFactory and MyFactoryManagement. It is not necessary to see details. The interaction maps shall just visualize how we made a plan to connect the drawings from Annex A1.6 in the interactive Axure prototypes.

Figure 8: Interaction map of MyFactoryManagement App

The interactive prototype was evaluated by four workers of Sunlight. The evaluation was conducted as usability testing with thinking aloud and contextual inquiry. The goal was to find usability issues and to improve the understanding of the context of use.

The interview analysis can be found in Annex 6 of the second version of D1.1 - User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines. Within this, 10 new user needs

were found. In addition, several constraints for deployment were identified. The usability test detected 90 critical situations according to ISO Normative Formalisation.

The evaluation results were used for designing the second version of the interface.

3.1.3 2nd Version

For the second version, a clickable HiFi-prototype was created using Invision. For this, images were created with JustinMind Prototyper. Invision was used for making them interactive. The clickable prototype can be found here: <https://invis.io/XN5M757FJ>

Exemplary texts for suggestions and categories were used based on input from Sunlight.

Master/Start Screen

Figure 9: Suggestions system, 2nd iteration, start screen

The start screen (cf. Figure 9) consists of three columns, to the left we have the categories, the middle column contains buttons for adding a new suggestion to the corresponding category.

The third column contains the suggestions. If more than 3 suggestions exist for a category, scrolling-arrows appear on the edges.

On the bottom of the screen is a text field for searching for suggestions.

Info Screens

MyCOMAU		Suggestions for Improvement		
Production Process Improvement		Suggestions concerning the production line, the schedule and the resources involved in the production process.		
Equipment and Facilities	Add New >	Better lighting in workplace ✓ ACCEPTED		
Human Resources	Add New >	Getting More Feedback	Sharing Experiences with...	Digital Vacation Registration ✓ ACCEPTED
Existing Product Improvement	Add New >	OCR-A font Labels for Robot Cases	New color for robot body 2 COMMENTS	
New Product Idea	Add New >	Robot Arm for Drone		
Health and Safety	Add New >	Lunch break optimization 3 COMMENTS	Sidewalks missing in the... ✓ ACCEPTED	
Other Ideas	Add New >	Soccer tournaments... ✓ MODIFIED	Good Weather Short Working... × REJECTED	Ice cream at least once a week 2 COMMENTS

Fraunhofer FIT Search

Figure 10: Suggestions system, 2nd iteration, info screen

There are info screens (cf. Figure 10) describing each category and one general info screen describing the app. The general info screen is reached via clicking the MyComau-Area.

The category info screens can be reached by clicking on the respective category. All info screens open as overlays; the general info spanning over the complete right side of the screen (Add- & Suggestions-area) and the category info spanning over the left columns of the category line.

Details Screens

< Equipment and Facilities

Better lighting in workplace

✓ ACCEPTED

Lighting in the workplace is not very well distributed, so a better reorganization will help operators to work in a more comfortable way.

2 COMMENTS

We also could use brighter lights.

I agree, the current lighting is very strenuous on the eyes. This is not healthy!

Write your comment...

 Add Comment

Date: 16.09.2016
Suggestion forwarded to:
 Mr. Marco Abate

Figure 11: Suggestions system, 2nd iteration, details screen

< Other Ideas

Bring your dog to work-day

✗ REJECTED

Reason
This is a nice idea for an office environment. In our case however, unfortunately this is not possible due to safety concerns.

NO COMMENTS YET
Be the first to write a comment!

Write your comment...

 Add Comment

Many of the workers have dogs and it would be nice, if we could bring them to work once a week.

Date: 16.09.2016
Suggestion forwarded to:
 Mr. Davide Abandonato

Figure 12: Suggestions system, 2nd iteration, details screen

< Production Process Improvement

Digital manuals / Mechanical Drawings

✓ MODIFIED

Modifications
 First we will need to determine to what extent this would be used, so we could start with just one terminal and see how much it will be used by the workers.

There should be terminals placed near our workstations that we can use to access the digital manuals and mechanical/construction drawings. These manuals can contain all the useful information needed to perform the assigned tasks.

Date: 16.09.2016
 Suggestion forwarded to:
 Mr. Andrea Benini

3 COMMENTS

I would prefer to use a tablet!

I guess tablets would be to expensive...

Why do we need a computer to do this? I prefer to work with paper-based manuals and plans. The way we do it now is totally OK.

Write your comment...

Figure 13: Suggestions system, 2nd iteration, details screen

< Human Ressources

Sharing Experiences with others

⌚ PENDING

NO COMMENTS YET

We would like to have more possibilities to share our experiences and what we learned from these experiences. In this way other workers can learn from other's mistakes and also can improve themselves.

Be the first to write a comment!

Write your comment...

Date: 16.09.2016
 Suggestion forwarded to:
 Ms. Francesca Accosi

Figure 14: Suggestions system, 2nd iteration, details screen

The detail screens (cf. Figure 11 - Figure 14) are reached by clicking on a suggestion in the master-view. Here the user can view all the available detailed information for the respective suggestion. Comments concerning the suggestion are also displayed and new comments can be added. The detail screen contains two columns, which are scrollable on demand. On the top bar of the detail screen, we have a back-button for going back to the master view.

Also the view contains (not implemented) navigation arrows on the left and right border of the screen for navigation the suggestions in this category.

Contact Information

<
⚙️
Production Process Improvement

Digital manuals / Mechanical Drawings

✓ MODIFIED

Modifications

First we will need to determine to what extent this would be used, so we could start with just one terminal and see how much it will be used by the workers.

There should be terminals placed near our workstations that we can use to access the digital manuals and mechanical/construction drawings. These manuals can contain all the useful information needed to perform the assigned tasks.

Date: 16.09.2016
Suggestion forwarded

Mr. Andrea Benini

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Office 345, Building A5, 3. Floor

3 COMMENTS

I would prefer to use a tablet!

I guess tablets would be to expensive...

Why do we need a computer to do this? I prefer to work with paper-based manuals and plans. The way we do it now is totally OK.

Write your comment...

✎ Add Comment

Figure 15: Suggestions system, 2nd iteration, contact information screen

The contact information (cf. Figure 15) for a decision maker can be viewed by clicking on the contacts name in the detail view. Contact information is presented as overlay.

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Add Suggestion

MyCOMAU

Production Process Improvement

Equipment and Facilities

Human Resources

Existing Product Improvement

New Product Idea

Health and Safety

Other Ideas

Describe your suggestion: ✕

Good suggestion

This is a really nice suggestion for you to consider. I think it will improve the work situation for everybody greatly.

Add Photo

Add Suggestion

Fraunhofer FIT

Figure 16: Suggestions system, 2nd iteration, add suggestion screen

Upon clicking “Add suggestion” in the master view, the user is directed to the “Add Suggestion” form (cf. Figure 16), which opens as an overlay (Note: here leaving the overlay by outside-click does not work in the prototype due to technical restrictions of InVision).

The respective category is highlighted. In the form, the users can enter a title and a description for their suggestion (not possible in prototype due to technical restrictions). In addition, they can add a picture (not implemented in the prototype).

By clicking close, they discard all information; displaying a warning is not necessary. If any of the text fields is left blank, a warning is displayed and the form will not be sent (not possible in prototype due to technical restrictions).

Upon clicking “Add suggestion”, a confirmation overlay is displayed.

Confirmation overlay

Figure 17: Suggestions system, 2nd iteration, confirmation overlay

The confirmation overlay (cf. Figure 17) contains a short confirmation text and the information of the responsible decision maker.

After a few seconds it redirects to the master screen (not possible in prototype due to technical restrictions), but it can also be closed immediately by clicking anywhere on the screen.

Overlays

All overlays close on click of the respective close button and on outside click.

3.1.4 Evaluation of the 2nd Version

After finishing the second design iteration, we used the prototype described in Section 3.1.3 again to conduct a user study. This time, the user study was conducted at Comau, so that both pilot plants are covered. As described in Section 3.1.3, the design was implemented as a clickable prototype using Invision. (It can still be tested here: <https://invis.io/XN5M757FJ>)

The prototype was evaluated by five workers of Comau. It was conducted as interview and usability testing with thinking aloud. The goal was to enhance the understanding of the context of use and evaluate the current version of the prototype to boost both the understanding and further improvement of the developed product.

The interview analysis can be found in Annex 6 of the second version of D1.1 - User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines. During this analysis, 84 individual insights together with possible implications were identified. The main results are summarized in Section 2.4.3 of D1.1 - User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines.

The evaluation results were used for designing the current version of the interface.

3.1.5 3rd Version

In the 3rd version, the following changes were mainly conducted.

- Adjusted colour scheme because the original colours were oriented on the SatisFactory colours but had the disadvantage to convey meanings (warning colours) which were not intended
 - Google Material Design colours were used as guidance
 - Interface now less colourful, with more prominent colour accents on key components
- Categories now less prominent
 - Visually reduced
 - Choosing a category moved to the end of the "add-suggestion"-process
- Comment-section was removed
- Timeline view introduced
- "Show info"-Interaction was removed and category information was added to the "add-suggestion"-form instead
- One central "Add suggestion"-button on overview-screen
- Re-added start screen from 1st Version of the prototype (Iteration 3)

Start Screen

Suggestions for improvement

Figure 18: Suggestions system, 3rd iteration, start screen

To avoid users being overwhelmed by the wealth of information of the overview-screen, we re-added the start-screen (cf. Figure 18), which was introduced in the 1st Version of the prototype (cf. Annex A1.1 -A1.6).

Here the user can choose between creating a new suggestion straight away (without being confused by all the categories) and viewing the overview-screen.

Overview Screen

Figure 19: Suggestions system, 3rd iteration, overview screen

One user need was to see "how long a suggestion has been in the system". To address this, we introduced a duration-based representation of the creation date (minutes / hours / days / weeks / months since creation). Other dates (modification, state change) will not be shown, since they do not represent information essential to the user. The overview screen (cf. Figure 19) shows all suggestions in a timeline view, starting from the newest suggestion. Old suggestions stay in the system, but are pushed back in the timeline.

The categories are now less prominent in order to focus the user on the suggestions. Choosing of a category is now at the end of the creation process. In addition, due to the change of moving the categories backwards in the creation process, there is just one prominent "add-suggestion"-button.

Figure 20: Suggestions system, 3rd iteration, overview screen filtered

The view can be filtered by state (cf. Figure 20). Given the timeline view, an additional date-based filtering is obsolete.

Add new suggestion (overlay)

Figure 21: Suggestions system, 3rd iteration, add new suggestion screen, initial state

Figure 22: Suggestions system, 3rd iteration, add new suggestion screen, filled out

When accessed from the start-screen the overlay will simply present itself as a card on white background. When accessed from the overview-screen, the overview-screen will be visible in the background (fade).

When no text is entered, the "add suggestion" button is inactive. Only when title and description are entered it will activate (cf. Figure 21).

The "add photo"-button was removed, since with a fixed kiosk we have no possibility of adding photos.

Choose category

Figure 23: Suggestions system, 3rd iteration, choose category screen

Choosing a category before entering their suggestion proved to be a barrier to users. Removing the categories was not an option, so we opted for reversing the process in order to lower this barrier. In addition, the category information was added, so no additional interactions are necessary. In order

to signify that a category **MUST** be chosen, the "add suggestion"-button will remain inactive until the user does so.

Suggestion Details (Overlay)

Figure 24: Suggestions system, 3rd iteration, suggestion detail screen

The comments were removed since the evaluation results show us, that most users were just confused by them and they will most likely not get used a lot (or get misused).

This led to the detail view (cf. Figure 24) having a reduced information volume, which now gives us the opportunity of representing it with an overlay. The top part contains information concerning the suggestion itself, whilst the lower part contains all information concerning the decision process.

3.2 CURRENT DESIGN

The current version does not differ much from the 3rd version prototype. The following changes were done:

- Free-text search
- Up- and down voting. This replaced the comment function as feedback channel. Furthermore, it is used as connection to the gamification framework (cf. D2.3 - Social

Experience and Gamification techniques for increasing attractiveness and D3.4 - Collaborative platform for work process support).

- Minor layout changes

The MyFactory version is implemented as a fixed worker kiosk for submitting suggestions. The kiosk will be a tablet computer. The MyFactoryManagement will be a web application that is usually accessed by managers from their office computers.

1. Add a suggestion

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Describe your suggestion:". It contains three input fields: "The title of my suggestion is...", "I suggest...", and a large empty text area for the description. A blue button labeled "SAVE SUGGESTION" is positioned in the bottom right corner of the form.

Figure 25: Suggestions system, current version, add suggestion screen

2. After describing the suggestion, it must be assigned to a category

Choose a category:

Production Process Improvement
Suggestions concerning the production line, the schedule and the resources involved in the production process

Equipment and Facilities
Improvements related to workplace facilities and equipment.

Human Resources
Improvements addressing organizational or contractual issues and company's culture.

Existing Product Improvement
Your ideas for improving existing products.

New Product Ideas
Your ideas for new products.

Health and Safety
Preventive measures and treatment of issues related to healthcare and safety.

Miscellaneous
Ideas related to any other topic.

SAVE SUGGESTION

Figure 26: Suggestions system, current version, choose category screen

3. All suggestions can be viewed.

← BACK Suggestions Overview

+ NEW SUGGESTION Show: ACCEPTED MODIFIED REJECTED PENDING Search

CATEGORIES	SUGGESTIONS			
Production Process Improvement	Digital manuals 8 months ago 7 votes ✓ MODIFIED	Visualization of W... Invalid date 0 votes ⚙ PENDING	VR Training glasse... Invalid date 1 votes ✗ REJECTED	
Equipment and Facilities	More coffee ... a few seconds ago 0 votes ★ NEW	More Comfortabl... a year ago 22 votes ✓ ACCEPTED	Canteen Opening ... Invalid date 4 votes ⚙ PENDING	
Human Resources	Getting More Fee... a year ago 14 votes ✓ ACCEPTED	Sharing Experienc... 6 months ago 3 votes ⚙ PENDING	Digital Vacation R... a year ago 0 votes ⚙ PENDING	
Existing Product Improvement	No suggestions in this category			
New Product Ideas	No suggestions in this category			
Health and Safety	No suggestions in this category			
Miscellaneous	No suggestions in this category			

Figure 27: Suggestions system, current version, overview screen

4. Checking and unchecking the statuses in the upper centre filters suggestions by status

Figure 28: Suggestions system, current version, overview screen filtered by status

5. The search box in the upper right can be used to filter for keywords

Figure 29: Suggestions system, current version, overview screen filtered by keyword

6. Clicking a suggestion opens the details view. In that view, the suggestion can be up voted or down voted.

Figure 30: Suggestions system, current version, detail screen

The next things we plan to implement are:

- Translate texts to Greek and Italian
- Make language customizable from within the app
- Add login functionality
- Add more categories

4. DESIGN OF THE GAMIFICATION FRAMEWORK

The idea behind the gamification framework is to have a central framework that handles the backend details of all the gamified Satisfactory components. The components communicate with this central gamification framework using REST calls. The gamification framework is designed to have two types of score visualizations. One is for individual points of each worker and the other is for displaying collective points of all the workers.

4.1 INDIVIDUAL POINTS VISUALIZATION

The purpose of the individual points visualization is to make the worker aware of his current status. This status includes information regarding the games he is currently participating in. Also, the individual points visualizer will enable the user to monitor his progress in each game separately.

4.1.1 Design Iterations

This section contains the iterations of design approaches adopted to visualize the individual points of the worker.

4.1.1.1 1st Iteration (MyScore App)

MyScore is a web application, designed to visualize the individual score of the worker. Figure 31 shows the prototypes of the MyScore app. It consists of two parts. One is the visualization of the score of the worker for each game separately. The star represents the maximum score that can be reached in that particular game. This maximum score can be entered by management or might as well be the highest score obtained by any other worker in this game. Another part of the interface involves the avatar evolution (See Avatar Evolution for details).

Figure 31: MyScore Mobile App

The prototype evolved into a web application that communicated with the central gamification framework to get the worker's score for each game separately and displayed it in a very simple manner.

Figure 32: My Score Web Application

4.1.1.2 2nd Iteration (Social Collaboration Platform)

The idea of having an individual score visualizer evolved from a web application to integrating it with the social collaboration platform, where the worker can view his status. Figure 33 shows the status of the worker. The worker can choose to “Join” or “Leave” any game. Also, he can view his current points in any particular game.

Figure 33: Status of Individual Worker

Using this interface, the worker can also view the high scores of other workers “In the Crowd”. The purpose of this section is to serve as motivate the worker to perform better by showing how well others are doing.

Figure 34: Top Achievements from the Crowd

The interface also provides information regarding the Awards and Badges. It also informs the worker as to how he can attain these badges e.g. if your answer score is over 10 then you are awarded the “Tutor” award. Figure 35 shows details of various badges available to the worker.

Figure 35: Badges and Awards

4.1.2 Avatar Evolution

The individual points visualizer contains a very important concept of avatar evolution. This concept follows an interesting way to show the worker how much progress has he made. This serves as motivating the worker to participate more and attain higher levels. The idea is to have an initial avatar assigned to the worker. As he participates in various games by interacting with various gamified Satisfactory components, he will gain more points and will be able to reach new levels. With each progress the avatar will evolve to something new. Hence, showing the worker that he has made some progress.

4.1.2.1 1st Iteration

The idea of avatar evolution was first designed by having different images of Football players. The levels of the game would correspond to the world ranking of these player. The better the level, the better the player in the worker's avatar.

Figure 36: Avatar Evolution using Footballers

4.1.2.2 *2nd Iteration*

The idea evolved to having icons instead of actual images of football players. These icons evolve into a better ranked employee. So, the progress of the worker in the games corresponds to the professional progression of the icon. The better the level, the better the professional rank of the worker.

There are two advantages in comparison to the first iteration. Firstly, we ran into copyright issues with the football players. Secondly, the idea with the football players arose from the gathered requirement that nearly all interviewed workers were enthusiastic about football. Nevertheless, we wanted to have a generic version of avatars, which everybody is able to do something with.

Figure 37: Avatar Evolution using Icons

4.2 *COLLECTIVE POINTS VISUALIZATION*

The collective points of all the workers will be displayed using the digital andon system. The idea is to have the collective points displayed on a screen that is publicly viewable.

4.2.1 *Design Iterations*

The collective points visualizer is intended to make the workers aware of the points obtained as a collective effort. The intention is to invoke and encourage a sense of team spirit. At the same time, it acts as additional motivation factor to increase the team points by conducting gamified actions.

4.2.1.1 *1st Iteration*

The first idea for the collective point visualizer was to divide the workers in teams and letting them compete with each other. Each team using various gamified Satisfactory components and gaining points for them. The collective points of all the workers in a particular team are displayed on the collective points visualizer. As visualization device, a public display is used that as many workers as possible pass by. This way, a general awareness of the current state of the game is achieved. The display also shows the collective points of other teams. Hence, invoking a sense of competition. Teams can be declared winner on the basis of these collective points.

Figure 38: Collective Point Visualization with Team Competition

4.2.1.2 *2nd Iteration*

The idea of having a collective points visualizer with team competition evolved into having a winning streak instead. Reason was to avoid having to declare any team “The Loser Team”, which would lead to demotivation as the Satisfactory end user partners told us from past experiences. So, instead the collective points visualizer will consider all the workers as a part of the same team. Each worker who interacts with the gamified Satisfactory components, gains some points as a result. All of these results are accumulated and displayed collectively on the Collective Point Visualizer. As the day passes, today’s score becomes yesterday’s score and everyone has to compete with their own cumulative score from the previous day. Thus, encouraging a sense of team work by avoiding the situation where there will be any losers. Figure 39 shows a scenario where the workers collectively

gained 85 points the previous day and are ready to start with the new day. The green thumbs symbol shows that they were able to beat their previous score. The highest score here is the highest cumulative points ever attained by all the workers. Since the goal is to beat yesterday's score over and over again, this is called a win streak approach. If one day, yesterday's score was not beaten, a new streak begins from 0.

Figure 39: Collective Point Visualization with Winning Streak

4.2.1.3 *Implemented Design*

The win streak approach explained in Section 4.2.1.2 was implemented using the Digital Andon System as public display. Hence, the gamification framework calls the Digital Andon API every time the team points get updated in order to refresh the output of the team points visualization. The activity flow of this procedure is described in Section 2.2.4 of Deliverable D3.4 - Collaborative platform for work process support. Figure 40 shows the visual output.

Figure 40: Team points visualization with digital andon

4.3 *PROTECT YOUR HEALTH*

The modified soap dispenser (Figure 41) is basically a common soap dispenser for industrial use enhanced with customized electronic mounted inside the housing. The device is intended to detect when the button that is used to get served with soap, is pressed. To achieve that, two electrodes are positioned in order to touch each other allowing current flow from one electrode to the other. As soon as the button in the front is pressed one electrode moves breaking the connection between these electrodes. Two wires which are connected to the electrodes are leading out of the housing to a Raspberry Pi which is able to detect when the electrodes inside the soap dispenser are disconnected. Hence, detecting that someone has pressed the button. The purpose of this device is to encourage the workers to protect their health by keeping their hands clean.

Figure 41: Gamified Soap Dispenser

Protect Your Health is a gamified SatisFactory component. It means that every time a worker washes his hands, he will obtain certain amount of points as a result.

5. AR-GLASSES

5.1 OVERVIEW OF THE AR GLASSES

The AR Glasses is an augmented reality eyewear that allows an operator to see the reality in front of her and, at the same time, see data coming from an ERP or enterprise software through the wireless network to the AR device (cf. Figure 42). The augmented reality effect is obtained by putting a flat glass with a 45° inclination in front of the eye of the operator, and projecting an image over it.

Figure 42: The AR glass device

The SatisFactory project could benefit from the AR Glasses to further increase the attractiveness of the gamification framework, by automatically showing the information about the implemented gamification tasks in a more convenient and easy way. Also, having a light-weight and easy-to-use REST API allows external developers to fully integrate the functionalities of the software with the glasses, without being bound to a specific programming environment or framework.

5.2 SUGGESTIONS PLATFORM

In regards of the suggestion platform, we could show a notification to the operator whenever one of the events that yield points is activated. This is very important, because workers could be encouraged to explore all different actions giving points, and discover associated icons or text shown through the eyewear.

All notifications can be shown in specific timeframes (during coffee breaks, or 5 minutes before the end of the shift, etc.) to avoid distracting the worker during dangerous work procedures, and in any case with a very low priority as notifications should not hide or interrupt critical alerts.

In the following mockups, examples of what could be achieved is shown: in the first case (cf. Figure 43), one of the suggestions created by the worked has been upvoted by a colleague and the device is showing the points obtained.

Figure 43: Visualizing an event on the AR glasses

5.3 *MYSCORE APP*

The MyScore App is an application that shows the gamification profile of the worker and the scores for the associated games. In this case, upon request of the operator the eyewear could show to the worker her profile and other statistics for the games, such as the scores, the most recent score obtained, etc.

In the mockup in Figure 44, another case is shown: the operator has gained enough points to increase her level from 4th to 5th, so that the transition between the two levels is displayed on the eyewear.

Figure 44: Visualizing a level increase on the AR glasses

5.4 *PROTECT YOUR HEALTH*

In the “Protect your Health” game, the team is competing against itself as explained in the previous chapters. Therefore, it is important to show to the whole team when a milestone is reached. In the mockup in Figure 45, a notification about the achievement is shown. As stated before, those notifications should be at a very low priority and only be informative, so that they appear on the glasses only for a few seconds. All those parameters (when to show the notification and for how much time) are at the developer’s discretion and should be analysed based also on the feedbacks of the operators.

Figure 45: Visualizing a milestone on the AR glasses

6. CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of the present deliverable is to document the iterative process of the interface design for a few selected concepts that were formulated in order to achieve the fundamental goal of increasing the attractiveness of the working environment for the workers. This deliverable described how these designs evolved with each iteration and what caused these changes. The selected concepts include the Gamification Framework, the Suggestions for Improvement Platform, The Social Interaction Platform and the Protect your Health System.

D3.2 explained the evolution of the user interfaces for various platforms designed to encourage the social interaction between workers in factories. For example, the social interaction platform aims to improve the social aspect of the working experience for the workers. The gamification framework aims to introduce a sense of playfulness and competition to stimulate collaboration and motivate workers for doing tasks better or more frequent. This deliverable also described how the workers can benefit from having hands free interaction with the system using the Augmented Reality Glasses.

Conclusively, this deliverable documented the details of interface design of various systems and the iterative process following which these interfaces evolved into their current state. The concepts behind these systems and some others are documented in D2.3 - Social Experience and Gamification techniques for increasing attractiveness. The corresponding implementation details are explained in deliverable D3.4 - Collaborative Platform for Work Process Support.

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ANNEX

A1.1 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT, 1ST VERSION, 1ST ITERATION, 1ST DESIGN

CATEGORIES

For which category would you like to submit a suggestion?

AUTOMATION	BUILDING FACILITIES	ELECTRICAL
INFORMATICS	MAINTENANCE	PROCESS
SAFETY		

CATEGORY NAME

Please type in your suggestion.

[← BACK TO CATEGORIES](#) [SUBMIT SUGGESTION →](#)

A1.2 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT, 1ST VERSION, 1ST ITERATION, 2ND DESIGN

 CATEGORY NAME

Please type in your suggestion.

SUGGESTIONS	SUGGESTION DETAILS
7 would like bla bla ... >	<div style="text-align: right;"> 2 votes </div> " I would like to "
_____ >	Status:
_____ >	Submitted to:
_____ >	Submission Date:
_____ >	Category:

A1.3 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT, 1ST VERSION, 1ST ITERATION, 3RD DESIGN

A1.4 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT, 1ST VERSION, 2ND ITERATION

Worker's Interface

Submit A Suggestion

SHOP FLOOR CATEGORIES

For which category would you like to submit a suggestion?

 AUTOMATION			

CATEGORY NAME

Please type in your suggestion

 BACK TO CATEGORIES

 SUBMIT SUGGESTION

View All Suggestions

Admin Interface

Add a New Category

Edit an already existing category

 HOME

EDIT A CATEGORY

Choose a Category to edit :

 HOME

UPDATE "Category Name" CATEGORY

Category Name : Image :

Suggestions will be submitted to :

Receiver's Name : Image :

Receiver's Email Id :

BACK TO THE MAIN MENU

UPDATE CATEGORY

Delete an already existing category

Receiver's Interface

View all suggestions submitted to me

Suggestion Details

Accept suggestion with modifications

Reject suggestion with reasoning

Add Collaborator (Send Collaboration Request)

+

ADD COLLABORATOR

△

Please enter information about the collaborator.

Name : (oblig)

Email :

←
 Back to Suggestion Details

+
 Add Collaborator

View received collaboration requests

○

COLLABORATION REQUESTS

△
HOME

Mr. Bla Bla requests your collaboration for: a suggestion

View Suggestion Details
✓ Accept
invitation
✗ Reject
invitation

Mr. Bla Bla requests your collaboration for: a suggestion

View Suggestion Details
✓ Accept
✗ Reject

←

 CATEGORY NAME

Please type in your suggestion

BACK SUBMIT

SUBMISSION SUCCESSFUL!

Thank you for submitting your suggestion.
Your suggestion has been forwarded
to Mr. Bla Bla.

A1.5 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT, 1ST VERSION, 3RD ITERATION

Worker's Interface

Submit a Suggestion

View All Suggestions

View Suggestion Details

Admin Interface

Add a New Category

Edit an already existing Category

Receiver's Interface

View All Suggestions submitted to Me

View All Suggestions

View Suggestion Details

Accept a Suggestion with Modification

Reject a Suggestion with Reasoning

Add a Collaborator (Send a Collaboration Request)

View Received Collaboration Requests

View Suggestion Details upon receiving a Collaboration Request

A1.6 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT, 1ST VERSION, 4TH ITERATION

MYFACTORY APP

Main

Suggest an Improvement

Help Screen (After pressing on the question mark)

View Submitted Suggestions

< Back Submitted Suggestions

New Product Idea	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Existing Product Improvement	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Infrastructure Modification	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Production Process Minor Modification	<	Barcode Reader for Order IDs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Production Process Major Modification	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Human Resources	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Administration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>			

< Back Production Process Minor Modification

PENDING

Barcode Reader for Order IDs

In the traction battery assembly department we need to compare the order IDs on different assembly parts in order to find all the parts of an order. Currently we are doing it manually. This is tiresome and not efficient. It would be good to have barcode reader system for this step. Thanks!

Responsible
Ms. Ifigenia Angelis, Mr. Dimitrios Nicolas

9-10-2015

+ 2 Comments

 Add Comment

2/15

Add comment for a suggestion

MYFACTORYMANAGEMENT APP

Login Screen (After pressing on the Lock-icon on the main screen)

Main

Add comment:

After "Accept" has been pressed (to prevent unintended triggers):

Reject a suggestion:

Accept with Modifications:

Invite collaborators:

View Collaboration Requests:

